

Automated Lip Reading from Video Dataset with 3D Convolutional Neural Network

ONGOING WORK

Tashin Ahmed^{1*}, Lasmin Sultana Shormi^{2†}, Ali Mostakim Alvi^{2†}, K.M. Arif Uz Zaman²

¹Independent Researcher

²The University of Asia Pacific, Dhaka, Bangladesh

tashinahmed@aol.com, (19101086, 19101015, 19101030)@uap-bd.edu

Abstract

Lip reading from videos or images using deep learning-based solutions is becoming increasingly necessary to solve a variety of tasks, especially for physically challenged people. As the world's sixth most widely spoken language, Bengali (Bangla) is still far behind other languages in terms of technological progress. In this work, using video data we produced (in preparation), we attempt to find a solution to solve the lip-reading problem in Bengali using a 3D Convolutional Neural Network (3D-CNN). So far, we are testing different Machine Learning (ML) and Deep Learning (DL) based models' performance from a private synthetic dataset (English) that we will publish soon.

Introduction

Automated Lip Reading (ALR) through AI aims to detect words from a person through video data without audio or image sequences caught by a camera. There has been an increasing interest in developing ALR systems mostly with DL (Fenghour et al. 2021). This type of system can be useful for hearing-impaired people to understand what others are saying in front of them through IoT devices (Assael et al. 2016). Also, it can be useful for next-generation subtitle creation on online video streaming platforms. There is a lot of work out there in this domain for various languages, but almost none in the Bengali language and almost 9.6% of the population of Bangladesh (a Bengali-speaking country) is deaf or has a hearing loss of 40 dB or more (Tarafder et al. 2015). Our work might become the pioneer in helping this vast community.

Dataset

We are working on two different datasets. Primarily, we are working on a synthetic video dataset that is built on 400 different word vocabularies. A sample of the dataset is demonstrated in Figure 1. Our main dataset is in the Bengali language, which we are creating right now. We are hopeful to collect around 2000 data ($2000 \times 3 = 6000$ seconds) consisting of 50 different Bengali words. For 10 random words from the vocabulary, the counts of data have been shown in

*Non-student advisor and collaborator

†These authors contributed equally.

Figure 1: 10 frames from a sample synthetic data (colored), Extracted face of above samples with MediaPipe (grayscale). Word in the sample data is "wait".

Figure 2A. Frame density and count for the whole dataset have been shown in Figure 2B.

Implementation

To extract faces from video frames, we have applied the MediaPipe framework (Lugaresi et al. 2019). The sample output of MediaPipe has been shown in Figure 1. 10 color images are representing 10 different frames from 1 second video and the grayscale images are the output from the MediaPipe face detection model for the same frames.

We have followed different ML approaches from Scikit-Learn library (Pedregosa et al. 2011) and hyperparameters are tuned with the Optuna framework (Akiba et al. 2019). We have used Tree-structured Parzen Estimator (TPE) (Bergstra et al. 2011) as the sampler. After creating the ML based baseline we are working on DL based baseline and primarily worked on a handbuilt 3D-CNN (Ji et al. 2012) model.

Model		Accuracy	Precision	Recall	F1
Random Forest Classifier	Tuned with TPE Sampler	73.2 %	76.377 %	73.2 %	72.177 %
K Nearest Neighbors Classifier		24.2 %	26.161 %	24.2 %	22.443 %
Gaussian Naive Bayes Classifier		3.2 %	1.11 %	3.2 %	1.394 %
AdaBoost Classifier		0.2 %	0.0 %	0.2 %	0.001 %
Bagging Classifier		71.4 %	74.982 %	71.4 %	70.401 %
Handbuilt 3D-CNN		90.0 %	84.399 %	84.781 %	83.564 %

Table 1: Validation scores of different ML and DL based approaches.

Figure 2: A: Sample of 10 words data count; B: Frames count on whole (Primary Synthetic) dataset.

Figure 3: Our prospective refined network.

Evaluation and Results

Outcomes of different models have been shown in Table 1. For DL based experiments we have used maximum of MAX_FRAMES = 20 frames for each video data.

Conclusion and Future Work

In this paper, we are trying to work on existing state-of-the-art techniques on synthetic (primary investigation) and Bengali own house (created by us) datasets. We plan to evaluate our work on other datasets and try to propose a new perspective (Figure 3) refined network of our own in the future. Current repository - <https://github.com/TashinAhmed/mimicry>.

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